

Incidence of Blood Culture Confirmed Typhoid Fever and Antimicrobial Resistance Pattern of *Salmonella* Typhi in a rural population of District Faridabad, Haryana, India

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ABSTRACT

Background: Typhoid fever remains major public health concern yet the actual prevalence in rural Indian population is limited. **Objectives:** This study designed to estimate the incidence of blood culture–confirmed *Salmonella* Typhi infection in rural community. **Methodology:** A prospective community-based active fever surveillance system was planned from October 2019 to April 2021 at HDSS (Ballabgarh Health and Demographic Surveillance System), India for weekly household visits. Seven largest villages were selected maximizing population coverage. Blood samples of suspected cases were tested at tertiary care hospital. **Results:** The incidence rate of typhoid fever in 2 years of age was 17.7cases per 100,000 person-years of observation (95% CI 6.69- 28.79) [Median time to fever defervescence:14 days (interquartile range 7–17 days)]. 90% (9/10) were positive for *S. Typhi* and 10% (1/10) were identified as non-typhoidal *Salmonella* spp, All the isolates found susceptible to cephalosporins and azithromycin with reduced fluoroquinolone susceptibility. **Conclusion:** This study highlights the population-based active surveillance of typhoid fever cases in the rural India emphasizes the need of continues robust surveillance.

Keywords: Typhoid fever, *Salmonella* Typhi, Antimicrobial resistance, Community-based surveillance, Health and Demographic Surveillance System (HDSS), Active fever surveillance, Enteric fever, Blood culture.

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Introduction

Typhoid fever is a febrile multi-systemic infection caused primarily by *Salmonella enterica* serotype Typhi and Paratyphi A, B, and C. Globally, *Salmonella* Typhi causes 20 million new cases annually, most of which occur in low and middle-income countries^{1,2}. In 2019, an estimated 9.2 million (95% CI 5.9-14.1) cases of typhoid fever were reported worldwide, with 110,000 (95% CI 53,000-191,000) deaths. Disease transmission occurs primarily through the faecal-oral route, involving consumption of contaminated food or water³. Department of Drinking Water and Sanitation, Ministry of Jal Shakti, Government of India, launched Jal Jeevan Mission (JJM) in 2014. The program aimed to provide a functional household tap connection (FHTC) to every rural household. The same Ministry launched Swachh Bharat Mission -Gramin (SBMG) in 2014. The aim was to make rural area “open

defecation free” (ODF) by constructing 100 million toilets in rural area by 2019 (Swachh Bharat Mission-Gramin)^{4,5}. Both these initiatives are likely to have impacted the incidence of all faecal-oral route transmitted diseases, including typhoid fever, in India.

Typhoid fever is indistinguishable from other febrile illnesses. Isolation of *Salmonella* from blood culture is considered the “gold standard” for diagnosis. Easy over-the-counter availability of antibiotics, self-medication, and widespread misuse of antibiotics has led to the development of antimicrobial resistance among *Salmonella* species. The antimicrobial resistance trends often reflect antibiotic usage patterns and the emergence and spread of genetic mutation⁶. However, a recent report suggests that there is re-emergence of susceptibility in *Salmonella* to chloramphenicol, ampicillin, and co-trimoxazole⁷. Nevertheless, they are no longer recommended as first-line treatments due to the ongoing risk of multidrug resistance (MDR)⁶.

The recent changes in availability of safe drinking water and improved sanitation, along with ever changing landscape to antibiotic susceptibility pattern in *Salmonella* species is likely to have clinical as well as public health policy implications⁸. However, data on community-based incidence rate and antibiotic susceptibility pattern of *S. Typhi* is scarce in India. Therefore, we conducted this study with the following objectives:

1. to determine the blood culture confirmed incidence rate of *Salmonella* Typhi infection among community-dwelling individuals older than two years; and
2. to determine the anti-microbial susceptibility pattern among *Salmonella* isolated from the blood culture of febrile community-dwelling individuals.

Methods

Study site: The study was conducted at the Ballabgarh Health and Demographic Surveillance System (HDSS). The HDSS consisted of 28 villages in Ballabgarh Tehsil of district Faridabad, Haryana. There were two Primary Health Centres (PHCs) that were staffed with medical doctors who offered comprehensive health services to the resident of these villages. Multi-purpose workers (MPWs; both male and female) made fortnightly domiciliary visits to collect health and demographic data. These data were then entered into a computerized Health Information Management System (HIMS) every month. In addition, annual census was done in the month of December and the HIMS was updated. Other health related personnel available in the village included Accredited Social Health Activist (ASHA), and registered medical practitioner (RMP) were also included. More detail of HDSS is available elsewhere⁹. Of the 28 villages, we selected seven villages with largest population size. The reason for not selecting all the 28 villages of the HDSS was to conserve resources. Selection of seven largest villages allowed inclusion of largest possible number of individuals under active surveillance with the least number of field worker requirement. All the seven villages included in the study had access to safe drinking water (piped water supply). Majority of the households (91.7%) were above the poverty line¹⁰. The poverty line represents the income level necessary to meet the minimum standard of living. Individuals with an income below this threshold are considered to be living below the poverty line.

As per the annual census 2018, the population of selected villages were as follows: Chhainsa (10,520), Jaya (5,729), Fatehpur Billoch (8,208), Atali (7,492), Dayalpur (6,824), Macchgarh (5,703), and Chandawali (5,715).

Definitions

Fever case: An individual who reported fever for 3 days and/ or body temperature $\geq 101^{\circ}\text{F}$ at the time of recruitment or normal body temperature if taking anti-pyretic medication.

Resolution of fever: Three consecutive days without fever in the absence of anti-pyretic medication.

Study period: Total study duration was from October 2019 to April 2021 with a break of 5 months i.e., from March 2020 to July 2020 due to COVID restrictions. Thus, the total effective follow-up period was 14 months.

Study population: The total population of the seven villages included in the study was 50,191. We excluded 1,877 children that were younger than 2 years. The remaining 48,314 individuals were eligible for active surveillance.

Setting-up of a community-based active fever case surveillance system: We set up an active fever case surveillance system. One field attendant (FA) was appointed to each of the seven study villages. The beat schedule was prepared in such a manner that each house was visited once a week by the FA who enquired about fever cases. To improve the completeness of fever case detection, ASHA, MPW, PHC doctors, and RMPs working in these villages were also requested to share with FA, if they had any information on fever cases. The FA assessed the eligibility of the reported/identified fever case. The FA administered a structured interview schedule, and provided a referral slip to the fever case. Cases were referred to the PHC where they were received by a study staff nurse.

The staff nurse collected venous blood from the fever case and then escorted the case to the PHC doctor for further management of fever. The blood sample was transported to the Microbiology department at the All India Institute of Medical Sciences, New Delhi, under cold-chain for further processing. The FA delivered the blood test report at the house of the participants who were then advised to share it with their treating physician.

Follow up: Till the time the report of the blood culture became available, monitoring of patients' health was done either through home visit or phone. Patients with blood culture positive for *Salmonella* Typhi were visited weekly to record the treatment outcome till the fever resolved.

Laboratory methods: We collected blood sample from patients with fever (5 ml from adults and 2-3 ml from children) aseptically in BactAlert (BioMerieux, France) bottles. The BactAlert bottles were incubated in BactAlert automated microbial detection system and when the machine gave positive signal by blinking, further subculture was done on MacConkey (Himedia) and blood agar. Bacterial organism identification was done by MALDI TOF as per the manufacture's guidelines. Species characterization was done by standard biochemical tests, and sero-typing was done by using antisera from SSI (SSI Diagnostics A/S, Denmark). The BactAlert samples which were negative in the system were further sub-cultured after incubation of 7 days before reporting it as negative.

Antimicrobial susceptibility testing was done manually by Kirby Bauer disk diffusion method. Briefly, antimicrobial susceptibility was tested for chloramphenicol (30µg), cotrimoxazole (1.25/23.75 µg), amoxicillin (10 µg), ciprofloxacin (5µg), pefloxacin (5µg) and cefixime (5µg) ceftriaxone (30 µg) followed by azithromycin (15µg) as per the Clinical Laboratory Standards Institute (CLSI) guidelines 2019.

Minimum inhibitory concentration (MIC) for ciprofloxacin, levofloxacin, ofloxacin, azithromycin, cefixime and ceftriaxone was determined by E-Test strips (bioMérieux, France) following manufacturer's instructions. *E. coli* ATCC 25922 was used as a quality control strain for disk diffusion, and MIC determination. All the isolates were stored as stab cultures in nutrient agar at 4°C and as glycerol stocks at -70°C for further molecular characterization.

All the laboratory work was done in NABL accredited laboratories. The laboratory staff were trained and experienced personnel.

Statistical analysis: Descriptive analysis was used to characterize fever cases. Because of COVID restrictions, interval censoring of surveillance period of five months (March to July 2020) was done. Thus, the calculation of person-years of follow-up was after excluding this period.

Ethical approval - The institutional Ethics Committee of All India Institute of Medical Sciences, New Delhi, approved the study procedures and informed consent forms (Ref. No. IEC/NP-463/2012 & RP-18/2013, OP-7/06.04.2018).

Results

Surveillance cohort characteristics: A cohort of 48,314 individual, older than 2 years of age, and residing in the selected study villages, was assembled. The total follow-up duration was 14 months (Table 1). The total numbers of incident fever cases were 1,225 of which we could collect 1,134 (92.6%) blood samples.

Table -1: Reason for refusal consent

Total Refusal-91 cases	
10 cases	Eligible participant could not come to PHC for investigation because of lack of transport facility
58 cases	Participant refused for blood sampling due to lack of consent
10 cases	Children at age of 2-8 years investigation refused by parents.
13 cases	A febrile at the time of visit to eligible participant and refused by participant.

Table- 1(a): Monthly Screening and Sample Collection Overview for Typhoid Surveillance

Duration	Screening	Participant eligible	Sample collection done	Refusal	Positive
Oct-19	12,900	150	113	37	3
Nov-19	12,749	85	70	5	0
Dec-19	11,100	82	80	2	0
Jan-20	10,400	80	74	6	0
Feb-20	9,300	60	50	12	0
March-20	4,000	31	29	0	1
Jul-20	10,600	20	10	0	0
Aug-20	11,300	106	100	13	0
Sep-20	12,700	88	89	0	2
Oct-20	12,900	112	120	2	0
Nov-20	12,749	93	90	3	1
Dec-20	11,100	106	106	1	0
Jan-21	12,000	59	56	4	0
Feb-21	11,600	61	56	5	1
Mar-21	10,400	80	79	1	2
Apr-21	1,000	12	12	0	0
Total	1,66,798	1,225	1,134	91	10

Sixty-eight of the 91 refusals to provide blood specimen were due to the lack of consent. Other reasons for refusal were, patient was a febrile at the time of enrolment and hence did not consent for the blood test (n=13), and patient was unable to reach the PHC for blood test due to the lack of transport facility (n=10). A vast majority (37/91, 40.7%) of the refusals had occurred in the first month of surveillance. The age and sex distribution of fever cases who gave consent for blood samples, and those who refused were similar (data not shown). The refusal rate among males was slightly higher than females (7.9% Vs 7%).

Table 2: Demographic and statistical analysis of eligible patients by Age Group and Gender

Statistic	Total (1225)		Child (113)		Adolescent (112)		Adult (833)		Senior Adult (167)	
	Male (n=502)	Female (n=723)	Male (n=52)	Female (n=61)	Male (n=40)	Female (n=72)	Male (n=356)	Female (n=477)	Male (n=54)	Female (n=113)
Refusal cases	40	51	3	8	3	2	29	33	5	8
Samples Collected	462	672	49	53	37	70	327	444	49	105
Mean age	34.2	46.9	7.5	6.7	15.5	15.5	39	39	70	75
IQR age	26	49	5.5	6	3.5	3.5	21	21	11	16

Child= 0-12 years, Adolescence= 13-18 years, Adult= 19-59 years, Senior Adult= 60 and above

Characteristics of fever cases: Among the 1,225 incident fever cases, 723 (59.0%) were female Table 2. Fever case detection rate varied greatly. It was low in Chhainsa (7.4/1,000 population) and Fatehpur Billoch (13.8/1,000 population). However, much higher rates were observed in Atali (38.7/1,000) and Macchgarh (71.5/1,000) Table 3. For almost half (49%) of the fever cases, the duration of fever was 3-4 days, while another 40% had fever for 5-10 days (Supplementary Table 2). Fever ranged from low-grade to high-grade, with some patients experiencing very high temperature (104°C). Defervescence of fever typically occurred within two weeks of starting appropriate antibiotic therapy, such as ceftriaxone, or ciprofloxacin. Most patients experienced defervescence between the 14th and 17th day of treatment.

Table- 2(a) : Duration of fever and its incidence among participants

Duration	No. of Participants	%	Incidence per 100,000 - person year
3-4 days	597	48.73	1023
5-10 days	496	40.47	850
11-15 days	73	5.96	125
16-20 days	26	2.12	44
21-25 days	10	0.87	17
26-30 days	23	1.88	39
Total	1225		

Incidence of culture confirmed typhoid fever: The cohort of 48,314 individuals was followed-up for the duration of 14 months (1.17 years), resulting in 56,527 person-years of follow-up. The total number of blood culture positive typhoid cases detected during the surveillance period was ten, resulting in the typhoid incidence rate of 17.7 (95% CI 6.69- 28.79) cases per 100,000 person-years of observation (Fig 1). Among these ten typhoid fever cases, six were female. For typhoid fever cases, the median time to defervescence with appropriate antibiotic therapy was 14 days (interquartile range 7–17 days). Because of the small numbers of typhoid fever cases, no further sub-group analysis was performed.

Antibiotic use and sensitivity among typhoid fever cases: Among those fever cases who did provide samples for blood culture, an overwhelming majority (1120 of 1134, i.e., 98.7%) had availed allopathic treatment. Other treatment modalities availed included Homeopathy (n=11), Ayurveda (n=1), and home remedies (n=2) (Supplementary Table-3 & 4). Details of medication based on history and/or written documents were available for 867 of the 1,125 cases (70.8%). For the remaining 358 (29.2%) cases, use of medication, if any, was unknown. Among those cases where history of medication was available, 98 (11.3%) cases had taken antibiotic while 11 of 867 cases (1.3%) had taken cefixime, 17 (2.0%) had taken amoxicillin, one had ceftriaxone, and 69 (7.9%) had taken other antibiotics.

Table -3: Type of Antibiotic/ treatment Among Participants

Treatment type	Total no. of patients	
	No.	%
Participants taking only PCM	769	62.78
Participants taking PCM with amoxicillin	11	0.89
Participants taking PCM with Cefixime	17	1.39
Participants taking Ceftriaxone	01	0.08
Not Known	358	29.23
Other Antibiotics	69	5.63
Total	1225	100.0

Antimicrobial susceptibility pattern: Out of the 10 *Salmonella* positive blood specimens, 9 were identified as *Salmonella* Typhi while one was grouped as non- typhoidal Salmonellae. None of the 10 strains were multi-drug resistant (MDR) Table-4. One strain showed resistance to chloramphenicol and trimethoprim-sulfamethoxazole. A total of 4 strains exhibited intermediate susceptibility to ciprofloxacin followed by 4 strains that were resistant. All *S. Typhi* strains were susceptible to cephalosporins and azithromycin whereas *Salmonella* group B was susceptible to all the anti-typhoidal drugs except exhibiting intermediate susceptibility to ofloxacin. All *Salmonella* strains were complete susceptible to ceftriaxone and cefixime; however, MICs were observed to be at the higher end of the susceptible range.

Table-3(a) : Village-Wise Analysis of Typhoid Fever Surveillance Participation and Vaccine Coverage

Places	Sample collected		Refusal cases		Typhoid Vaccine	
	Male	Female	Male	Female	Yes	No
Atali	119	144	12	15	-	290
Chandawali	39	78	3	2	-	122
Chhainsa	23	52	-	3	-	78
Dayalpur	38	65	6	6	3	115
Fatehpur Billoch	41	65	4	3	2	111
Jawan	52	29	5	4	-	92
Machgarh	147	234	10	17	-	407

Table- 4: Antimicrobial susceptibility for typhoidal drugs in culture positive cases

AMA	Ballabgarh, Delhi 10)					
	S. Typhi 'n' 9			S. group B 'n' 1		
	S	i	r	S	i	r
Ampicillin	9	Nil	Nil	1	Nil	Nil
Chloramphenicol	8	Nil	1	1	Nil	Nil
Trimethoprim-sulfamethoxazole	8	Nil	1	1	Nil	Nil
Cefixime	9	Nil	Nil	1	Nil	Nil
Ceftriaxone	9	Nil	Nil	1	Nil	Nil
Ciprofloxacin	1	4	4	1	Nil	Nil
Ofloxacin	Nil	5	4	Nil	1	Nil
Levofloxacin	1	4	4	1	Nil	Nil
Pefloxacin	2	Nil	7	1	Nil	Nil
Azithromycin	9	Nil	Nil	1	Nil	Nil

Table-4(a) : Different treatment modality used in community

Variables	No.	%
Not Taking Any Other Treatment Modality	1120	98.7
Homeopathy	11	0.97
Ayurvedic	01	0.08
Home Remedies	02	0.17
Total	1134	

Discussion

We present here the findings from a community-based, active surveillance of fever cases among a cohort comprising of 48,314 individuals, older than two years of age, and residing in the seven selected villages of a rural area of district Faridabad,

Haryana. A study conducted in HDSS in January 2017, had revealed that the availability of sanitary latrine was high (84.8%). The proportion of household having a hand washing facility along with improved sanitation was also high (70.4%) in that part. The cohort was followed-up for a period of 14 months. The unadjusted incidence rate of typhoid fever case was 17.7 per 100,000 person-years.

The **NSSEFI** (National Surveillance System for Enteric Fever in India), from 2017 through 2020, conducted a multi-site study among children aged 6 months to 14 years. One of the sites (Pune) was a rural site similar to our study. The study period overlapped with our study period. However, the study populations were dissimilar because at Pune site, the recruitment was restricted to children only. The incidence rate of typhoid fever at Pune site was 35 (95% CI 9-89) per 100,000 child-year. Despite differences in the study population, the incidence rate of typhoid fever in our study (17.7 per 100,000 person-years) was close to the observation of Pune site (35 per 100,000 child-year).

Table -5: Demographic and Clinical Profile of blood culture positive Typhoid Fever Patients

Name & Age (yrs)	Gender	Place	Vaccination	Outside Travel history	Duration of fever Days	Defervescence/ Treatment	Organism
Kartik (5 yrs)	Male	Chandawali	No	Yes	22	14 th day of treatment	S. Typhi
Virender (51yrs)	Male	OPD	No	Yes	16	7 th day of treatment	S. Typhi
Rahul (21 yrs)	Male	Jawan	No	No	22	Amoxicillin, metronidazole for 7 days. 14 th day of treatment	S. Typhi
Monti (21 yrs)	Female	Atali	No	Yes	Not Tracked	Phone call was not answered and visit was not possible due to Covid-19	S. Typhi
Sarabjeet(18 yrs)	Male	Chainsa	No	No	58	Ceftriaxone, Tab Novoclav 625 mg BD) 14 th day of treatment	S. Typhi
Arti (27 yrs)	Female	Chainsa	No	No	40	Ciprofloxacin 15 th day of treatment	S. Typhi
Bala (75 yrs)	Female	Chandawali	No	No	45	14 th day of treatment. No treatment revealed by pt. No ab previous history	S. grp B
Ronak (20 yrs)	Female	Machgarh	No	Yes	19	14 th day of treatment Ceftriaxone and metro-nidazole	S. Typhi
Lakshmi (35 yrs)	Female	Fatehpur Billoch	No	No	21	Treatment was not disclosed by patient. 17 th day of treatment	S. Typhi
Akashy (25 yrs)	Male	Jawan	No	Yes	14	17 th day of treatment	S. Typhi

The incidence rate of typhoid fever could get affected by various factors including typhoid vaccination, and improvements in water and sanitation. Typhoid vaccination was not a part of the routine immunization. Hence, the study participants were naïve to typhoid vaccine. However, the availability of safe drinking water and sanitary latrine was high in the study area. Most participants belonged to upper socio-economic strata. Historically, economic upliftment coupled with improvements in safe drinking water and sanitary latrines have resulted in decline of infectious diseases, even in the absence of disease specific intervention. It is, therefore, reasonable to assume that these factors played a role in observed low incidence rate of typhoid fever despite the absence of typhoid vaccination in the study area.

Among febrile participants, the overall refusal rate to provide blood specimen was 7.4%, most of which (40.7%) was concentrated in the first month of the surveillance. Awareness generation among community members, coupled with training of the project field staff, greatly ameliorated the situation. For the rest of the surveillance period, the monthly refusal rate was in low single digit. Getting consent for blood collection, particularly from children, in field conditions is, in any case, a challenging task. That we were able to reduce the refusal rate following awareness generation, illustrates the importance of community preparedness prior to the start of any community-based research. No significant socio-demographic differences were noticed between those who consented and those who refused to give blood specimen. Low refusal rate after the first month of surveillance, coupled with non-differential refusal rate gives us the confidence to conclude that refusal to provide blood specimen did not adversely affect the validity of our findings.

The true incidence of typhoid fever is likely to be underestimated in the presence of widespread use of antibiotics. In our study, among those for whom the information on antibiotic use was available, the prevalence of antibiotic use during the current episode of febrile illness was relatively low (11.3%). The data was missing on the antibiotic use for almost one-third (29.2%) of the fever cases. We are unable to speculate any reason(s) to believe that those fever cases for whom information on antibiotic use were unavailable would be systematically different from those for whom the information was available. A little more than half (51.3%) of all fever cases had fever for a duration of five or more days. Therefore, ample opportunity was available to the fever case to initiate use of antibiotic, if they were so inclined. And yet, the rate of antibiotic use was low in this rural community. This was a reassuring finding when contrasted with the reported general trend of rampant misuse of antibiotics. In addition, the low rate of antibiotic use gave us confidence to conclude that we were unlikely to underestimate the incidence rate of typhoid fever in this rural community of Haryana.

Within four months of the start of the surveillance i.e., March 2020, COVID-19 was considered a public health emergency and the Government of India enforced complete restriction on physical movement. Other public health measures included forced quarantine of all fever cases that tested positive for COVID. There was widespread stigma and social exclusion of COVID-19 affected individuals and their families. The general public was greatly inconvenienced by these measures and tried to deliberately hide the history of fever, preferring to resort to self-medication. Hence, it is possible that there was large-scale underreporting of febrile cases. Such a situation not only could lead to low and varied rate of fever cases, but also underestimate of the true incidence of typhoid fever in our study.

Strengths and Limitations: Our study is one of the few studies that provide incidence rate of typhoid fever in India. The study area was well characterized. The electronic health management information system (HMIS) had data for the last three decades. Hence, enumeration of the population under surveillance was complete. Active surveillance for fever cases by project staff, supplemented by information provided by the field level health professionals, ensured near complete detection of fever cases. The laboratory investigations were performed at a laboratory that was NABL accredited. The laboratory personnel were well trained and experienced in the work they performed. Therefore, the ascertainment of outcome variability i.e., blood culture reports, may be considered valid. However, the study had certain limitations. A unique situation arose during the COVID-19 pandemic resulting in unprecedented public health response by Government of India. The resultant fear and stigma among general population could have led to significant underestimate of the incidence of typhoid fever.

Conclusions

The incidence rate of typhoid fever among community-dwelling individuals older than 2 years, residing in a rural area of Haryana in north India was 17.7/100,000 person-years.

Declaration of Interest: All the authors declare no competing interests.

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